

2024 International Conference on IoT and Related Technologies

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1st International Conference on IoT and Related Technologies

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Preface

Dear Colleagues and Dear Guests,

On behalf of the organizing committee, welcome to 1st international Conference on IoT and Related Technologies. This 1st edition of the ICIRT will take place in Abidjan in Côte d'Ivoire from January 18 to 19, 2024 on the site of Centre National de Calcul of Côte d'Ivoire (CNCCI). The conference aims to bring together leading academic scientists, researchers and research scholars to contribute to the strengthening of the sharing and dissemination of results of research programs and projects on IoT in West Africa in order to facilitate their valorisation. This conference will be an opportunity to strengthen and consolidate the collaboration between academics, industrialists, startups operating in the field of IoT and its related technologies in order to contribute to the achievement of some of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), namely SDGs n°2, n°3, n°12, n°13, and n°15. Thank you very much for your interest in international Conference on IoT and Related Technologies.

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1- Keynote addresses

Keynote n°1

- **Title:** Interoperability in IoT
- **Keynote speaker:** Prof. Laurent Toutain
- **Affiliation:** IMT Atlantique/Rennes, France
- **Biography :** Laurent Toutain is Professor at Télécom Bretagne in the Network, Security and Multimedia Department. He is the head of the OCIF team (Objets communicants Internet du Futur -- Communicating Objects Future Internet). He has been working for many years in IPv6 (IPv6 Integration, auto-configuration...). He is a founding member of the G6 group, which regroups, since 1995, the French-speaking researchers on IPv6. He is currently working on the domain of Internet of Things. His research interests are on the evolution of the IP protocols and architectures to fit IoT needs and the applicability to Smart Grid. Since 2012 he manages the Smart Grid Competence Center jointly with Texas Instruments and Itron.

Keynote n°2

- **Title:** LoRaWAN Joins the DANCE: Mutually Authenticating End Devices and Backend Servers
- **Keynote speaker:** Mr. Ibrahim Ayoub
- **Affiliation:** Université Paris-Saclay/Paris, France
- **Biography :** Ibrahim Ayoub is Phd Student at Université Paris-Saclay. Also, he is Research And Development Engineer at AFNIC (Association Francaise pour le Nommage Internet en Coopération). He is currently working on the domain of DNS security. His research interests include Artificial Intelligence, Computer Communications (Networks), Computer Security and Reliability.

2- Research Papers

Detection of Threats Related to Android Malware Through Machine Learning

Doffou Jerome Diako^{1,3*}, Dje Bi Dje Guy Gabin^{2,4}, Patrice Mensah^{2,4}, Souleymane Oumtanaga^{2,3}

¹ Ecole Supérieur Africaine des TIC, ABIDJAN (Côte d'Ivoire)

² Institut national polytechnique Félix Houphouët-Boigny

³ LASTIC,

⁴ LARIT.

*Corresponding author: jerome.Diako@esatic.edu.ci

Abstract. Android malware poses a growing threat to security as it can cause significant damage to the computer systems of businesses. These malicious programs perform destructive functions with the aim of harming a target system, such as banks, telecommunications companies, online businesses, etc. Given that the majority of today's transactions are conducted via smartphones, the impact of Android malware is substantial. An Android malware is a program implemented by cyber attackers to exploit known and unknown vulnerabilities in smartphones to propagate successful infections. This article, titled "Detection of Threats Related to Android Malware through Machine Learning," focuses on the use of machine learning techniques to detect and counter threats associated with Android malware. The objective of this article is to develop effective real-time detection methods for Android malware, relying on Machine Learning algorithms. The algorithms utilized include logistic regression, decision trees, random forests, k-nearest neighbors, and gradient boosting. Our study is based on the Android malware dataset (CIC-AndMal2017). Experimental results demonstrate that the use of certain Machine Learning algorithms, such as decision trees, random forests, k-nearest neighbors, and gradient boosting, predicted the detection of threats related to Android malware with an average accuracy rate of 98%, recall of 98%, and precision of 98%. The obtained results support the use of these techniques to enhance computer security and protect systems against Android malware attacks.

Keywords: Malware, Machine learning, CIC-AndMal2017

Predictive Analysis for Monitoring HT/LT Substations Using Sensor Data

Siriki Traoré^{1,2}, Ali Kobenan^{1,2}, Armel Keupondjo^{1,2*}

¹INP-HB UMRI MSN, Laboratoire de Recherche en Informatique et Télécommunications (LARIT).

²Institut National Polytechnique Félix Houphouët Boigny de Yamoussoukro

*Corresponding author : siriki.traore@cie.ci

Abstract. Electricity is an essential resource for the development of a country. Access to electricity ensures the improvement of living conditions in households, fundamental services such as education by bringing light to schools and universities, food safety through refrigeration, access to communication technologies, or the enhancement of productivity in agricultural, industrial, and economic activities in general. The provision of electrical energy thus becomes one of the major concerns given its strategic importance and long-term impact. However, this requires appropriate infrastructure, namely the construction of production sources (hydroelectric dams, thermal power stations, etc.), the establishment of a network of overhead and underground power lines (underground cables, galleries, transformers, poles, overhead conductors, overhead transformers, lampposts, etc.) for the transport and distribution of energy. Such installed infrastructure, therefore, requires a robust and efficient control system to ensure high availability. The supervision of electrical installations involves monitoring, controlling, and automating the management of electrical networks. The supervision system is automated by collecting and processing data (measurements, alarms, availability, etc.) from sensors (IoT) placed on the electrical network. Indeed, these sensors and instruments include voltage sensors, heat sensors, material availability sensors, meters, circuit breakers, fire systems, distribution boards, microcontrollers, and many others.

The objective here is to implement a supervision system using IoT data from the distribution network to perform analyses and real-time forecasts. To do this, we utilize data from sensors integrated into HT/LT substations. Additionally, to gain an understanding of the profession and available data, we explored literature on the field of electrical energy while engaging in discussions with industry experts.

This approach allowed us to better comprehend the subject, especially the complexity of available data and possible approaches to solving the problem. In particular, we applied numerous machine learning algorithms and techniques, including methods dedicated to time series, supervised machine learning methods, and neural networks. For the selection of the best models, we used performance evaluation criteria such as RMSE (Root Mean Square Error) and MAE (Mean Absolute Error).

Keywords: IoT, Supervision, QoS, Sensor.

Using Sensor Data Variational auto-encoder for Image Processing in IoT Applications

Atiampo Kodjo Armand^{1*}, N'Takpé Tchिमou Euloge²

¹Unité de Recherche et d'Expertise du Numérique(UREN) , Université Virtuelle de Côte d'Ivoire,
Abidjan , Côte d'Ivoire,

²Laboratoire de Mathématiques et Informatique(LMI), Université Nangui Abrogoua, Abidjan, Côte
d'Ivoire,

*corresponding author : armand.atiampo@uvci.edu.ci

Abstract. New telecommunications networks are enabling powerful AI applications for smart cities and transport. These applications require real-time processing of large amounts of media data. Sending data to the cloud for processing is very difficult due to latency and energy constraints. Lossy compression can help, but traditional codecs may not provide enough quality or be efficient enough for resource-constrained devices. This paper proposes a new image compression and processing approach based on variational autoencoders (VAEs). This VAE-based method aims to efficiently compress images while still allowing for high-quality reconstruction and object detection tasks. The encoder is designed to be lightweight and suitable for devices with limited computing power. The decoder is more complex and uses multi-level vector quantization to reconstruct high-resolution images. This approach allows for a simple encoder on edge devices and a powerful decoder on cloud servers. Key contributions include a low-complexity encoder, a new VAE model based on vector quantization, and a framework for using VAEs in IoT. The first experiments on reconstructed images on CelebA and ImageNet100 datasets show promising results in terms of MS-SSIM and FiD compared to the literature and the ability of our approach to be used in various tasks like image classifications.

Keywords: Variational Auto-Encoder, Vector Quantization, Super-tokens.

Contribution of a Data Mining Method for the Detection of Fraud Risks Relating to Customs Clearance Operations

Pacôme Brou^{1*}, Bi Bolou Zehero¹, Thomas Kouassi²

¹Ecole Supérieure Africaine des Technologies de l'Information et de la Communication (ESATIC),
Laboratoire des Sciences et Technologies de l'Information et de la Communication (LASTIC),
Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire,

²Institut National Polytechnique-Houphouët BOIGNY, Ecole Doctorale des Sciences Techniques de
l'Ingénieur (STI), Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire,

*corresponding author : pacome.brou@esatic.edu.ci

Abstract. Customs risk reduction is a key challenge for most customs administrations. The conditions under which this mission is carried out depend both on the evolution of economic stakes and on the behaviour of those responsible for its implementation. The strong growth in trade and the development of ICTs have largely contributed to the digitization of customs administrations' information systems, with the introduction of storage systems dedicated to gathering information on customs clearance operations. Scrutinizing this risk-related information will certainly help to reduce the risk of fraud in connection with customs clearance operations, and in this context, we are using data mining methods to detect risks relating to customs offences. The aim will be to use a knowledge extraction method, Formal Concept Analysis (FCA), as a tool for classifying customs risks from a database of customs offences arising from customs clearance operations.

Keywords: Customs clearance, customs offence, data search

Deep Learning Models for Image Recognition: the Case of Tomatoes

Charlemagne N'diffon Kopoin^{1*}

¹Ecole Supérieure Africaine des Technologies de l'Information et de la Communication (ESATIC),
Laboratoire des Sciences et Technologies de l'Information et de la Communication (LASTIC),
Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire,

*corresponding author : charlemagne.kopoin@esatic.edu.ci

Abstract. The modernization of agriculture is associated with increased use of energy and inputs (fertilizers, plant protection products, water), which today need to be better managed to optimize their use and limit the risks to man and the environment. This issue has given rise to precision agriculture, a new approach to farming based on the integration of information and communication technologies, particularly IoT, in which the environment (soil, relief, etc.) is characterized in all its spatial variability, rather than being reduced in a conventional way to a homogeneous whole. In this work, we propose a deep learning model for tomato recognition based on sensor data. It must be said that this work falls within the field of e-agriculture, where we use artificial intelligence techniques for more efficient agriculture.

Keywords: sensor data, e-agriculture, artificial intelligence.

Load Balancing at Near-root Nodes in the RPL Protocol

Amian Etienne Bredou^{1*}, Niamien Thiéry Michaël N'goran¹, Joel Christian Adepo¹

¹Unité de Recherche et d'Expertise du Numérique(UREN) , Université Virtuelle de Côte d'Ivoire,
Abidjan , Côte d'Ivoire,

*corresponding author : amian.bredou@uvci.edu.ci

Abstract. Managing energy consumption in the Internet of Things is a challenge for researchers. A great deal of existing work is addressing this issue. Some propose solutions based on artificial intelligence. Others are based on improving existing routing protocols. The results obtained are promising, and the energy savings are remarkable. However, the majority of works cited in the literature propose a global optimization approach, throughout the network, to manage traffic flow. In doing so, bottlenecks are overlooked, especially around the convergence point. The aim of this work is to improve the RPL protocol by proposing a traffic balancing solution for nodes close to the root. This solution will improve network performance.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Routing Protocol, IoT

Comparative Study of Artificial Intelligence Algorithms for Anomaly Detection in Cybersecurity

Kevin Koffi Kouamé^{1*}, Ludovic Yves Morel Mignimou Kpangnou Kone¹, Michael Kouame Kouassi¹,
Joel Christian Adepo¹

¹Unité de Recherche et d'Expertise du Numérique(UREN) , Université Virtuelle de Côte d'Ivoire,
Abidjan , Côte d'Ivoire,

*corresponding author : koffi2.kouame@uvci.edu.ci

Abstract. Detecting anomalies in networks, e-mails and computer systems is a challenge that cybersecurity researchers face on an ongoing basis. With the evolution of technology, attack methods have undergone significant mutation. This makes them difficult to detect and eradicate using traditional anomaly detection methods. Tackling this problem has led to the creation of several methods based on artificial intelligence. This paper presents a theoretical comparative study of artificial intelligence algorithms for anomaly detection in cybersecurity. It shows that the Hierarchical Extreme Learning Machine (H-ELM) algorithm is well suited to anomaly detection in cybersecurity.

Keywords: Cybersecurity, anomaly detection, artificial intelligence.

The Contribution of Machine Learning to Energy Optimization in SDNs

L. Kra^{1*}, D. Nabongo¹ O. Asseu²

¹Université Alassane OUATTARA, Bouaké. Côte d'Ivoire,

²Ecole Supérieure Africaine des Technologies de l'Information et de la Communication (ESATIC),
Laboratoire des Sciences et Technologies de l'Information et de la Communication (LASTIC),
Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire,

*corresponding author : kralgasaneouat@yahoo.fr

Abstract. With the advent of new paradigms such as connected objects, the number of smartphones and users (those who use them) has increased. Interconnecting all these devices according to their performance consumes energy (in terms of electricity or resources). SDN (Software Defined Network) consists in decoupling the control plane (the brain) from the data plane (the muscles). We've used it in our previous work to programmatically put unused network equipment ports to sleep. From the Internet of Things (IoT), we move on to cognitive computing, i.e. the ability of a machine to "imitate" human thought. In this paper, we use Artificial Intelligence (AI) where Layer 3 switches (routers) are programmed to mimic human behavior. We will therefore implement a new SDN architecture that integrates human behavior into the control plane. Equipment ports will learn to switch off when not in use, without human intervention. A knowledge base in the control plane will record all energy-saving strategy movements in the network. This will enable us to benefit from a reduction in energy consumption in terms of network resources and electricity. The results obtained will enable us to evaluate the contribution of machine learning to SDN.

Keywords: AI, SDN, Intelligence, Artificial, cognitive, energy, human, paradigms.

Intelligent, Service-Oriented Architecture for Optimizing e-Learning in Internet of Things Environments

Olivier Kragbi Petey^{1*}

¹Unité de Recherche et d'Expertise du Numérique(UREN) , Université Virtuelle de Côte d'Ivoire,
Abidjan , Côte d'Ivoire,

*corresponding author : kragbi.petey@uvci.edu.ci

Abstract. The paper presents a novel approach to optimizing the e-learning experience in Internet of Things (IoT) environments using an intelligent service-oriented architecture. Faced with the exponential growth of connected objects in educational domains, this research aims to solve challenges related to efficient resource management, learning personalization and adaptability to different learning contexts. The proposed architecture is based on interconnected intelligent services, exploiting data generated by connected objects to deliver optimized e-learning. The integration of the Internet of Things and artificial intelligence enables dynamic personalization of pedagogical content according to learners' individual needs. The results demonstrate a significant improvement in learning efficiency, learner engagement and educational resource management, illustrating the considerable potential of this intelligent architecture for optimizing e-learning in Internet of Things environments.

Keywords: Service-oriented architecture, artificial intelligence, Internet of Things, IT governance, e-learning.

Solving VRP using the Genetic Approach with Optimization of Intensification and Diversification Phases using Machine Learning

Moustapha Diaby^{1*}

¹Ecole Supérieure Africaine des Technologies de l'Information et de la Communication (ESATIC),
Laboratoire des Sciences et Technologies de l'Information et de la Communication (LASTIC),
Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire,

*corresponding author : moustapha.diaby@esatic.edu.ci

Abstract. In this paper we present a genetic approach to solving a VRP problem. The special feature of our approach is the use of a machine-learning algorithm to optimize the selection and mutation phases. The Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP) is one of the most widely studied combinatorial optimization problems. It poses the problem of visiting customers from a depot, using a fleet of vehicles, at minimum cost. Many variants exist. Historically, VRP is an extended version of the Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP), which involves visiting all customers with a single vehicle. VRP problems are NP-complete Complexity problems like the TSP problem. To solve large instances, we use metaheuristics. We use a genetic algorithm. To optimize the intensification and diversification phases, we use a machine-learning approach. automatic learning approach. A series of tests on data sets from the literature the relevance of this approach.

Keywords: genetic algorithm, machine learning, optimization problem, NP-complete problem, Traveling Salesman Problem.